

Pompano *Trachinotus ovatus* (Linnaeus, 1758) (Actinopterygii: Carangidae) – a new species for the Black Sea

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Abstract: One adult specimen of pompano *Trachinotus ovatus* (Linnaeus, 1758) was found along the Bulgarian Black Sea Coast. The specimen has been caught in June 2022 in a static fish trap near the town of Primorsko. This is the first record of this thermophilic species in the Black Sea waters, which is presumably related to the increased seawater temperatures in the region and represents significant northward range extension.

Keywords: Black Sea, Carangidae, increasing seawater temperatures, range expansion, *Trachinotus ovatus*

Introduction

The advance of the thermophilic fish from the Mediterranean into the Black Sea is a phenomenon often called mediterraneanisation which gained increasing attention recently, because these species are considered as good indicators of climate change. This expansion is direct evidence for the link between the climate change and the distribution patterns of Mediterranean Sea fish. A total of 51 species of Mediterranean fish, including the pompano *Trachinotus ovatus* (Linnaeus, 1758), were found to expand their distribution northwards (Azuuro, 2008).

T. ovatus is a marine pelagic-neritic fish from the family Carangidae. It often occurs in schools in coastal waters, where adults swim near the surface (Golani et al., 2006). It is usually found over sand or mud bottoms but occasionally enters lagoons (Balik et al., 2011). The species is distributed in the Mediterranean Sea and adjacent areas of the eastern Atlantic from Bay of Biscay, Morocco, Madeira, Azores, to the Gulf of Guinea (Hureau & Tortonese, 1973). It is found also in the Aegean Sea (Çelik & Oehlenschläger, 2005; Öğretmen et al. 2005; Fricke et al., 2007; Altin et al., 2015) and the Gulf of Corinth (Moutopoulos et al., 2013). *Trachinotus ovatus* was recently found in the Istanbul Strait, where two specimens were caught in Filburnu Bay (Bilecenoğlu

& Öztürk, 2019) and in the Dardanelles, where one specimen was caught near Kepez, Çanakkale Strait (Tuncer et al., 2020). These are the first records of the species from the Turkish Straits System, consisting of the Istanbul Strait (Bosphorus), the Marmara Sea and the Çanakkale Strait (Dardanelles) and connects the Black Sea with the Mediterranean.

In this study, we present the first record of *T. ovatus* from the Black Sea, which significantly expands its known distribution range.

Material and methods

One adult specimens of *T. ovatus* was caught by local fishermen in June 2022 in the Black Sea near the town of Primorsko, GPS coordinates: 42.30 N; 27.78 E (Fig. 1). The specimen was caught in a static fish trap (dalyan) and photographed immediately after the catch. The photo shows all typical characters of the fish and allows the correct species determination (Fig. 2).

Results and discussion

The caught specimen was not preserved by the local fishermen but was documented with a telephone cam-

Fig. 1. Map of the Black Sea area with the location where *T. ovatus* was found near the town of Primosko, Bulgaria.

era. After detailed analysis of the photos and videos we found that it belongs to the species *T. ovatus* and possesses all the following features typical for it (see Fig. 2): body moderately long and highly compressed, back greenish-grey, sides silvery with 3–5 vertically elongate black spots on anterior half of lateral line, dorsal-, anal- and caudal-fin lobes with black tips, lobes of soft dorsal and anal fins small, length of second dorsal fin base equal to length of anal fin base, scales cycloid and very small, lateral line slightly arched over pectoral fins and straight thereafter, upper jaw very narrow at posterior (Bauchot, 2003).

Although the ichthyofauna of the Black Sea is recently well investigated (Vasileva, 2007; Yankova et al., 2014; Nicolae et al., 2018; Abliazov et al., 2021; Manilo, 2021; Guskov et al., 2022) there is no data about the presence of *T. ovatus* in it. The specimen found near Primorsko, Bulgaria is the first and up to now the only record of the species in the Black Sea and represents significant northward range extension. It would be interesting whether the species

will be discovered in new areas in the Black Sea in the near future and whether it will be able to establish a permanent population in the region.

The northward expansion of Mediterranean thermophilic species is probably the most detectable biotic responses to the climate changes in the region. We believe that *T. ovatus* followed the natural way of penetration into the Black Sea migrating through the Bosphorus Strait, where it was recently detected (Bilecenoğlu & Öztürk, 2019). No doubt, the increasing of the seawater temperature in the area is the main driving factor for the expansion of the species. Over the last two decades, a climate-related range expansion of *T. ovatus* from southern to the colder northern parts of the Mediterranean Sea has been also observed (Dulčić et al., 1997). In this regard, its recent finding along the Bulgarian Black Sea coast is not unexpected.

According to Lloret et al. (2014), thermophilic species have three phases of colonisation (occasional occurrence, common presence and establishment).

Fig. 2. *Trachinotus ovatus* found in a fish trap near the town of Primorsko, Black Sea, Bulgaria: lateral view of the body.

On the basis of our recent finding, we considered *T. ovatus* as an occasional species in the Black Sea.

According to Guskov et al. (2022), a total of 25 new species of fish had been discovered in the Black Sea since 2014. They are predominantly Mediterranean immigrants mostly from the families Gobiidae and Sparidae. Thus, *T. ovatus* is another adding to this list of species.

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